

Naphthoxides of Titanium(IV)

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Compounds of composition $Ti(ONp)_nCl_{4-n}$ ($n=1\rightarrow 4$) and $Ti(ONp)_4.NpOH$ have been prepared by the reaction of titanium(IV) chloride and 2-naphthol (NpOH) in appropriate molar ratio in benzene under different experimental conditions. Molecular weight and IR studies show them to be dimer through naphthoxy bridges. TGA and mass spectral studies show the stability of different compounds.

UNLIKE metal alkoxides¹ and phenoxides²⁻⁴, very little information is available on the metal naphthoxides though their study provides an interesting factor of steric effect on the formation and reactivity of metal-oxygen bond. Naphthoxides of manganese(II) and aluminium(III) are known^{5,6}. Funk and coworker⁷ obtained naphthoxides of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) by the reaction of metal chlorides and 2-naphthol. Tungsten(VI) chloride and tungsten(V) bromide form naphthoxides of respective composition^{7,8}. Emeleus and Rao⁹ indicated that the halides of titanium(IV) and zirconium(IV) react with phenols and naphthols. Apparently, no systematic study has been carried out on the metal naphthoxides though they also have many industrial applications and provide an interesting comparative study. An attempt, therefore, has been made to isolate and characterise the naphthoxides of titanium(IV).

Experimental

2-Naphthol (NpOH) (B.D.H.) was twice recrystallised from hot carbon tetrachloride and the sample having melting point (122-3°) was used for the preparation of the compounds. Titanium tetrachloride (reagent grade) was distilled in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Compounds of composition $TiCl_3(ONp)$, $TiCl_2(ONp)_2$ and $TiCl(ONp)_3$ were prepared by mixing titanium(IV) chloride with 2-naphthol in 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 molar ratio, respectively in dry benzene. The resulting solutions were stirred well till there was no evolution of hydrogen chloride gas. However, in the case of the compound $TiCl(ONp)_3$, the components were heated occasionally below 60° to complete the reaction. Compounds of composition $Ti(ONp)_4$ and $Ti(ONp)_4.NpOH$ were obtained when titanium(IV) chloride (0.01 mole) was refluxed with 0.04 mole and excess of 2-naphthol, respectively in benzene till there was no evolution of hydrogen chloride gas. The first three compounds (Table 1), separated out as solids while the latter two were isolated by the addition of dry petroleum ether to the solution. The compounds were filtered, washed with dry petroleum ether and dried under vacuum.

Titanium in these compounds was estimated as titanium dioxide while chlorine by Volhard's method. Molar conductance values of their millimolar solutions in nitrobenzene were determined on Elico conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra of the compounds were scanned as nujol mulls or in KBr pellets using double grating infrared spectrophotometer, Perkin Elmer models 337 and 621. Thermogravimetric analysis of these compounds was carried out on thermogravimetric balance (Stanton, Model No. AD-2). Determination of molecular weights of the compounds was carried out cryoscopically by Beckman method and ebullioscopically using Gallenkamp ebulliometer. Mass spectrum was recorded using EI-MS mass spectrometer at 200°, the excitation energy being 70 eV.

Results and Discussion

The compounds isolated in the present studies are brown to dark brown high melting solids. They are moisture sensitive and change their colour on exposure to atmosphere. Stoichiometric composition of these compounds has been assigned on the basis of titanium and halogen (Table 1). These compounds are soluble in nitrobenzene, nitromethane, acetonitrile, etc. Molar conductance values of their millimolar solutions in nitrobenzene show them to be non-ionic. While the molecular weight determination of the compounds of composition $Ti(ONp)_4$ and $Ti(ONp)_4.NpOH$ cryoscopically in benzene and nitrobenzene suggest them to be dimeric, ebullioscopic determination in benzene indicated them to be monomeric, suggesting that at 81° the dimeric \rightleftharpoons monomeric equilibrium shifts to the right-hand side. In case of the compound of composition $TiCl(ONp)_3$, the molecular weight determination in nitrobenzene cryoscopically suggested it to be a dimer. Ebullioscopic measurement in this case was not possible because of its insolubility in any low boiling solvent.

The bands around 3600 and 3380 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(OH)$ in pure 2-naphthol¹⁰ has been found lowered to 3562 and 3358 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum of the compound $Ti(ONp)_4.NpOH$, suggesting that the phenolic oxygen of 2-naphthol

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE TITANIUM(IV) NAPHTHOXIDES

Compound	Colour	Melting point (°C)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)		Molar conductance in PhNO ₂ (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	Molecular weight Found/(Calcd.)	
			Titanium	Chlorine		PhH	PhNO ₂
TiCl ₂ (ONp)	Dark brown	339(d)	16.10 (16.18)	35.69 (35.79)	3.60	—	—
TiCl ₂ (ONp) ₂	Dark brown	324	11.79 (11.86)	17.47 (17.53)	3.40	—	—
TiCl(ONp) ₃	Brown	290	9.29 (9.37)	6.87 (6.92)	3.13	—	1002 ψ (1025)
Ti(ONp) ₄	Brown	182	7.70 (7.74)	—	1.15	603 (620)* 1209 (1240)	1211 ψ (1240)
Ti(ONp) ₄ .NpOH	Brown	163	6.25 (6.28)	—	1.42	740 (764)* 1498 (1528)	1500 ψ (1528)

d = decompose, * = ebullioscopically, ψ = cryoscopically.

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF TITANIUM(IV) NAPHTHOXIDES

Compound	ν (C=C)	ν (O-C)	ν (O-Ti)	ν (Ti-Cl)
NpOH	1625, 1600, 1460, 1380	3600*, 3380*, 1260	—	—
TiCl ₂ (ONp)	1629, 1606, 1464, 1386	1198	508	348, 346
TiCl ₂ (ONp) ₂	1630, 1608, 1465, 1387	1208	508, 510	344
TiCl(ONp) ₃	1638, 1620, 1468, 1391	1215	598, 512	340
Ti(ONp) ₄	1636, 1608, 1470, 1398	1220	602, 520	—
Ti(ONp) ₄ .NpOH	1635, 1617, 1462, 1392	3562*, 3358*, 1208	595, 510	—

* ν (OH)

is coordinated to the titanium atom. However, the bands due to ν (OH) are completely missing in the compounds Ti(ONp)₄, TiCl(ONp)₃, TiCl₂(ONp)₂ and TiCl₂(ONp) thereby showing the absence of phenolic OH group in them. The bands at 1625, 1600, 1460 and 1380 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν (C=C) in the phenolic ring¹⁰ shift slightly towards higher regions. Furthermore, the most important and strong band present at 1260 cm⁻¹ in pure 2-naphthol^{10,11} due to ν (C-O) stretching mode shifts to lower spectral region by about 50-60 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of these compounds. This may be attributed to the drainage of electrons from the ring to the metal through C-O bond. All important ir bands are given in Table 2.

Far ir of these compounds have been very helpful in throwing some light on their structures. In the case of compounds of composition Ti(ONp)₄ and Ti(ONp)₄.NpOH, there are two broad bands observed at 602 and 595 cm⁻¹ and 520 and 510 cm⁻¹ and these may be assigned to terminal ν (Ti-O)

and bridging Ti-O-Ti modes, respectively^{12,13}. No band is observed in the region 300-350 cm⁻¹ for these compounds, which excludes the possibility of the presence of any Ti-Cl band in them. Thus, based upon the two types of metal-oxygen stretching modes and molecular weight determination, the following structure may be proposed for the compound Ti(ONp)₄.NpOH wherein each titanium atom has attained octahedral environment.

In the case of the compound of composition TiCl(ONp)₃, in addition to the sharp bands at 598 and 512 cm⁻¹ assigned to terminal ν (Ti-O) and

bridging Ti-O-Ti bonds, respectively, intense and sharp band at 340 cm⁻¹ has also been observed. This may be assigned to terminal ν (Ti-Cl) stretching modes^{4,15}. No band that could be assigned to

bridging Ti-Cl-Ti bond expected to fall well below 300 cm⁻¹ has been observed. This suggests that in preference to chlorine bridging, naphthoxy group acts as a better bridging group possibly due to the size and mass effect. Thus, based upon the ir spectral studies and molecular weight determinations and earlier reports on the structures of chloroalkoxides¹⁴ and phenoxides¹⁵ of titanium involving ethoxy and phenoxy bridges respectively, the following dimeric structure may be proposed for TiCl(ONp)₃. Similar type of structures may be postulated for the compounds of composition TiCl₂(ONp)₂, TiCl₂(ONp) and Ti(ONp)₄ wherein each titanium atom has a trigonal bipyramidal environment.

In order to explore the possible modes of decomposition of these naphthoxides and to determine the relative strength of bonds, thermogravimetric analysis of these compounds was carried out under atmospheric pressure. Different intermediates have been postulated merely on the basis of the weight changes noted from the TGA curves shown in Fig. 1. Although the final product in all the naphthoxides studied is TiO_2 , it is difficult to comment precisely on the nature of the intermediates formed. The possible modes of decomposition may be postulated as :

Similar type of intermediates can be postulated in case of other naphthoxides. Formation of such intermediates gets support from earlier reports of titanium compounds. It is evident from thermal studies that these naphthoxides are fairly stable compounds, possibly because of polymeric structure and in preference to the titanium-chlorine bond, $Ti-O$ bond is retained. Nevertheless, since no analytical evidence of the composition of the intermediates could be obtained because of their unstable nature, the possibility of some other types of intermediates cannot be ruled out.

Mass spectral fragmentation of the compound of composition $TiCl_2(ONp)_2$ has also been studied and it has been possible to assign molecular weights to the various species in the gaseous phase, and to examine the fragmentation patterns for being used in the structure elucidation. Suitable fragmentation schemes have been suggested (Fig. 2) and these are supported by the appropriate metastable peaks. Similar fragmentation patterns for various coordination compounds have been reported earlier also^{16,17}.

Fig. 1. Thermograms of titanium(IV) naphthoxides.

Fig. 2. Fragmentation pattern of dichlorotitanium(IV) naphthoxide.

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